

Optimization of Array Tapers Subject to Transmit Constraints

Dan P. Scholnik

Naval Research Laboratory, Code 5341
Washington, DC

Abstract—Array tapers are traditionally used only on receive, as classical low-sidelobe tapers would result in a significant reduction in transmitted power and most transmit arrays lack element-level amplitude control. As modern arrays move towards solid-state transmitters distributed to each element there is a desire to more fully harness this flexibility. It has been previously shown that the transmit power loss can be reduced by designing tapers that upper-bound the coefficients while allowing a small number of inner array-factor sidelobes to remain unconstrained. That work is extended here to remove structural limitations of the prior algorithm, admit arbitrary combinations of peak and mean-square constraints on the weights and the array factor, allow controlled “overdriving” of some elements, and allow lower-bounding of the array weights to limit the dynamic range of the taper. These extensions are enabled through the use of second-order cone programming, a popular form of constrained convex optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Most phased-array antennas use one or more amplitude tapers on receive to manage array-pattern sidelobes. The most common tapers are derived from continuous current distributions, including Dolph’s Chebychev line source distribution [1] and Taylor’s line and circular distributions [2], [3]. These limit peak sidelobe levels with generally modest sensitivity losses.

On transmit, on the other hand, high-power phased arrays have rarely included amplitude tapering. The primary obstacle has been hardware limitations. Older arrays used a small number of high-power transmitters and passive distribution networks to feed the elements, which do not allow efficient programmable amplitude tapering. Newer “active” arrays have smaller transmitters at each element, but these are still usually run in saturation for efficiency without any mechanism for amplitude control. This restriction seems likely to be overcome in the future, however, with the increasing popularity of bias-modulation architectures [4], [5] that enable efficient amplitude modulation.

The other major obstacle to amplitude tapers on transmit is the sensitivity loss due to a reduction in effective radiated power (ERP). Active arrays are typically limited by the peak power capability of the transmitter at each element, so that power not expended by an element with a small taper value cannot be readily shifted to an element with a larger taper value. The result is that classical low-sidelobe tapers like Dolph’s or Taylor’s cause a significant loss of ERP, on the order of 5 dB in one dimension and potentially double that in two dimensions, when used with peak-limited transmitters. Receive arrays do

not have a corresponding limitation, and thus suffer only from the much more modest (≈ 1 – 2 dB) mismatch loss of the taper.

In recognition of these transmitter limitations, several authors have looked at optimizing tapers subject to peak coefficient constraints for uniform linear arrays [6]–[9] and continuous circular apertures [6]. The major finding of these papers is that loss of ERP can be substantially reduced by allowing one or more inner sidelobes to remain unconstrained while suppressing the outer sidelobes in a peak or rms sense. The size of this unconstrained sidelobe region can be varied to trade off outer sidelobe suppression and ERP.

Two quite different optimization methods have been applied to this problem. In [6], [7] a constrained least-squares (CLS) algorithm was used. Although very efficient and convex, thus guaranteeing a global solution, the CLS solution has a couple of drawbacks. First, as formulated it restricts the tapers to a central peak-limited plateau with the peak constraint inactive elsewhere. As will be seen, this is not always the case for optimal tapers. Second, it is somewhat inflexible: it requires a quadratic objective and it is not straightforward to add additional constraints, such as limits on peak sidelobes. In [8], [9] CLS is compared to an alternative formulation using simulated annealing (SA), which is a non-gradient-based “global” optimization method. SA has no relevant restrictions on the objective, here a weighted sum of several metrics of interest. As formulated in [9] there is also no built-in assumption on the taper amplitude profile. SA also has drawbacks. First, as used here it is an unconstrained method, and thus requires tweaking the relative weights of the objective terms to get desired values at optimality. More fundamentally, SA is too general for the problem at hand. All of the metrics of interest — peak and rms sidelobes, peak coefficient value, ERP loss — are linear or quadratic in the taper coefficients, which are continuously valued. An appropriate gradient-based constrained convex programming solver that can take advantage of the problem structure would be expected to converge to the global solution much faster than the stochastic-based SA.

An optimization framework that fits the bill is *second-order cone programming* (SOCP) [10], which minimizes a linear objective subject to any number of linear and convex-quadratic constraints. SOCP is widely used for FIR filter [11] and array-pattern design [12]. Several fast and efficient interior-point solvers are available, both free [13]–[15] and commercial [16], [17]. Several high-level Matlab toolboxes are also available [18]–[20] that interface with these solvers. Using SOCP we

need not assume a particular form for the optimal taper, although relevant symmetries can be used to reduce the problem size without loss of generality.

We extend the existing work in several ways. First, by using SOCP the restriction to flat-top responses can be removed, as is the need to iterate to determine the plateau's extent. As will be seen, the optimal responses are often not flat. Using SOCP also allows for a variety of other constraints. Second, element-weight upper bounds greater than unity are considered, representing the ability to "overdrive" some elements. This is done in conjunction with an additional constraint to prevent an increase in total power. Third, we consider also lower bounds on the array weights, for situations where the dynamic range of the array coefficients should be limited. Finally, 2D taper designs are considered.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Let $a(\mathbf{x}_n)$ be an arbitrary complex-valued phased-array taper defined on a finite set of spatial positions $\{\mathbf{x}_n\}$. The corresponding array factor is a Fourier transform:

$$A(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} a(\mathbf{x}_n) e^{j \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{x}_n}, \quad (1)$$

where vector \mathbf{u} represents normalized spatial frequency. In the sequel we will assume a nominal upper bound for a of $1/N$, so that for a uniformly illuminated boresight beam we have the convenient normalization $A(\mathbf{0}) = 1$.

We wish to optimize the array taper according to:

$$\min_{a, \delta} \delta \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } A(\mathbf{0}) = A_0 \quad (2b)$$

$$\left(\int W(\mathbf{u}) |A(\mathbf{u})|^2 d\mathbf{u} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq \delta \quad (2c)$$

$$\sup_{\mathbf{u}} \{M(\mathbf{u}) |A(\mathbf{u})|\} \leq 1 \quad (2d)$$

$$\|a\|_2 \leq \sqrt{P_{\max}} \quad (2e)$$

$$\|a\|_{\infty} \leq a_{\max} \quad (2f)$$

Here auxiliary optimization variable δ provides a linear objective, required for SOCP. Constraint (2b) sets the ERP loss relative to uniform illumination to the value $A_0^2 \leq 1$. The constant A_0 is chosen to be positive real without loss of generality, since both $|a|$ and $|A|$ are invariant to complex rotation. The left side of (2c) represents the sidelobe energy in the pattern, weighted across spatial frequency by nonnegative real function W . This value is effectively minimized when combined with (2a). Constraint (2d) bounds the peak pattern sidelobes, with M another nonnegative real weighting function. Constraints (2e) and (2f) limit the total and per-element transmit powers. We will use $P_{\max} = 1/N$ throughout, which represents the total power resulting from uniform illumination.

Problem (2) is not in standard SOCP form, but can be straightforwardly mapped to same as outlined in [11]. Constraint (2d) is semi-infinite as written, but in practice will be converted to a possibly large but finite number of SOC

constraints by discretizing \mathbf{u} . Constraint (2f) is likewise mapped to one individual constraint per array element, and (2c) and (2e) each represent a single SOC constraint.

Many permutations of the basic problem are possible; for example, we could make any of the constraints (2d)–(2f) into the objective by replacing the constant on the right side with a function of δ and making the right side of (2c) constant. We also need not have both constraints (2c) and (2d).

If we were to remove constraint (2f) from (2) we would be left with a formulation mathematically identical to traditional receive-taper design, where (2e) serves to limit noise gain rather than transmitted power. Accommodating the peak-power constraint will generally require different weighting functions W and M than would be typical in receive taper design, as shown in the following example.

III. EXAMPLE

To illustrate how the peak-weight constraint affects taper design, we now consider an example design. We assume a planar array of identical elements, located at the 1069 points of a hexagonal lattice with $\lambda/\sqrt{3}$ interelement spacing that lie within a radius of 10λ from the origin. We shall set our ERP loss to 2 dB via $A_0 = 10^{\frac{-2}{20}}$, and set the weight upper bound to $a_{\max} = 1/N$. The sidelobe region is defined by setting W to unity over one period of the array factor, excluding a circle of radius 15° about the origin. The weighting function M is set to the value $10^{\frac{45}{20}}/A_0$ on the same support as W , effectively requiring peak sidelobes in the sidelobe region to be below -45 dB with respect to the peak of the mainbeam. The symmetry of the problem is such that the optimal taper will be real and even symmetric, as shown in the Appendix.

The problem was setup using the Opt Matlab toolbox [18] and solved using the SeDuMi SOCP solver [13]. The resulting array factor is shown in the rightmost plot of Fig. 1. Here the white lines indicate contours of constant azimuth and elevation at 15° intervals, with the outer circle delimiting visible space and the circumscribing red hexagon bounding one period of the array factor. The smaller red circle indicates the sidelobe region boundary. We can see that 15° encompasses the first several sidelobes, which are not suppressed. This is the fundamental tradeoff required to achieve reasonable ERP losses. For comparison, the left and center plots of Fig. 1 show the array factors corresponding to uniform weights and to Taylor's circular weighting with a sidelobe level of -40 dB and $\bar{n} = 5$. To assist the visual comparison all three patterns are normalized by their respective mainlobe heights $A(\mathbf{0})$, and the indicated sidelobe metrics are likewise with respect to the mainlobe. The Taylor pattern has low sidelobes everywhere and comparable sidelobes to the optimized pattern outside of 15° , however it has a likely unacceptable ERP loss of 8 dB. This is typical of traditional receive tapers when used on transmit.

The optimized weight distribution is shown in the right plot of Fig. 4, and contrasted with the Taylor weight distribution on the left. Both are normalized with respect to a_{\max} . The Taylor weights taper monotonically away from the center, while the optimized weights remain near 0 dB over most of the array.

Fig. 1: A comparison of uniform, 40 dB circular Taylor, and optimized array factors.

Fig. 2: A comparison of 40 dB circular Taylor and optimized array tapers.

However, contrary to the assumption of [6], [7], the optimal taper is not flat-topped; it has ripple including at the center.

IV. OVERDRIVEN ELEMENTS UNDER A TOTAL POWER CONSTRAINT

Setting the peak bound a_{\max} to its nominal value $1/N$ models an array that is independently peak-limited at each element. This is representative of typical active array designs today. More flexible architectures, however, could allow individual elements to be driven beyond their nominal peak levels, subject to a limit on total transmitter power. This would represent a shift of supplied power from the underdriven elements to the overdriven ones. Such architectures may be enabled by the emergence of new technologies; for example GaN as the material of choice for RF power amplifiers, in part because of its robustness to physical and electrical stress. Such an approach could further reduce ERP losses due to amplitude tapering.

Whenever the total power bound (2e) is inactive (i.e. $\|a\|_2^2 < 1/N$), the resulting taper is simply a scaled version of a peak-limited design with proportionally lower values of A_0 and a_{\max} . Thus we focus here on designs in which this total power constraint is active. Far from being independent, constraints (2b), (2e), and (2f) can all be related to each other using the relationship $\|x\|_q \leq \|x\|_p \leq N^{\frac{1}{p}-\frac{1}{q}}\|x\|_q$ for $0 < p < q$, which

is derived from Holder's inequality. In particular, we have

$$A_0 \leq \|a\|_1 \leq \sqrt{N}\|a\|_2 \leq N\|a\|_\infty \quad (3)$$

with equality holding across the board when all weights are identical. Thus the nominal weight upper bound of $a_{\max} = 1/N$ dominates the total power bound $P_{\max} = 1/N$, making (2e) inactive. Increasing a_{\max} above this level is a necessary (but not sufficient) condition for an active (2e). On the other hand, increasing A_0 greater than one guarantees that (2e) is violated, thus rendering (2) infeasible. Thus while overdriving as defined here can reduce ERP losses, it cannot improve ERP over uniform illumination.

To demonstrate the advantage of overdriven elements under a total energy constraint, consider the following permutation of (2):

$$\min_{a, \delta} -\delta \quad (4a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } A(\mathbf{0}) \geq \delta \quad (4b)$$

$$\sup_{\mathbf{u}} \{M(\mathbf{u})|A(\mathbf{u})|\} \leq 1 \quad (4c)$$

$$\|a\|_2 \leq \sqrt{P_{\max}} \quad (4d)$$

$$\|a\|_\infty \leq a_{\max} \quad (4e)$$

Here negating the objective (4a) and bounding the peak of the mainlobe below by δ in (4b) effectively maximizes ERP. For variety and simplicity, this time the sidelobe energy constraint is omitted. Now we fix $P_{\max} = 1/N$ as before, define the sidelobe region and weighting function M as in the example of Sec. III, and optimize with both nominal and overdriven values for the peak element weight: $a_{\max} = 1/N$ and $a_{\max} = 10^{2/20}/N$. The resulting array factors and tapers are shown in the first two plots of Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively. The primary difference is the improvement of ERP by 1.3 dB; the limit on total weight energy prevents the overdriven taper from realizing the full 2 dB of overdrive gain. Otherwise the two array factors are visually similar, with the overdriven array factor having somewhat higher inner sidelobes. Comparing the corresponding tapers in

Fig. 3: A comparison of normalized array factors for a nominally driven array taper and two tapers overdriven by 2 dB. In the first overdriven taper the sidelobes are fixed with respect to the nominally driven pattern, and in the second the ERP is fixed.

Fig. 4: A comparison of array tapers, corresponding to the array factors of Fig. 3.

Fig. 4, we see some similarities in structure but that they are not simply scaled version of each other.

Overdriven elements can be used to improve sidelobes instead of (or in addition to) improving ERP. Consider yet another permutation of (2):

$$\min_{a, \delta} \delta \quad (5a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } A(\mathbf{0}) = A_0 \quad (5b)$$

$$\sup_{\mathbf{u}} \{M(\mathbf{u})|A(\mathbf{u})|\} \leq \delta \quad (5c)$$

$$\|a\|_2 \leq \sqrt{P_{\max}} \quad (5d)$$

$$\|a\|_{\infty} \leq a_{\max} \quad (5e)$$

with M as before, overdriven elements given by $a_{\max} = 10^{2/20}/N$, and $A_0 = 10^{-1.5/20}$ to match the optimal ERP from (4) for the non-overdriven drive case. The resulting array factor and taper are seen in the third plots of Figs. 3 and 4. Here, for the same ERP, the overdriven weights have allowed a much smoother, flat-topped taper and an array factor with much deeper sidelobes. A continuum of designs lies between the two overdriven designs. Although not explored here, yet another option is to reduce the radius outside of which the sidelobes are constrained.

V. DYNAMIC-RANGE CONSTRAINTS

One of the drawbacks of both classical tapers and tapers optimized according to (2) is that they can have a large dynamic range $\max(|a|)/\min(|a|)$. There is a strong relationship between peak/rms sidelobes and dynamic range, such that tapers with low sidelobes will also have high dynamic range. As hardware often limits the actual available range, it is useful to be able to constrain the dynamic range directly, rather than simply allowing the sidelobes to rise until the available range is reached.

Consider the optimization problem

$$\min_{a, \delta} \delta \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } A(\mathbf{0}) = A_0 \quad (6b)$$

$$\left(\int W(\mathbf{u})|A(\mathbf{u})|^2 d\mathbf{u} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq \delta \quad (6c)$$

$$a_{\min} \leq a(\mathbf{x}_n) \leq a_{\max}, \quad n = 1, \dots, N. \quad (6d)$$

Here we assume our coefficients are real and positive¹, and constrain the dynamic range by adding a lower bound to the earlier upper bound on their magnitude. The peak-sidelobe

¹Strictly speaking, requiring positive coefficients is an overconstraint. However, only pathological designs appear to cause negative coefficients, and lower bounding the magnitudes of bipolar coefficients is not convex.

constraint has been dropped here for simplicity, although it can be retained in general.

Enforcing the lower bound a_{\min} on the taper a is equivalent to defining a in terms of the decomposition $a = a_p + a_t$, where $a_p(\mathbf{x}_n) = a_{\min}$ is a fixed constant pedestal and a_t is a nonnegative taper with no dynamic-range constraint. Because of the “discontinuity” of the pedestal a_p at the array edge we expect the sidelobes of the corresponding array factor A_p to largely determine those of the overall pattern A . It is interesting to consider the extent to which the taper sidelobes can be reduced below this nominal bound.

Consider Fig. 5, which shows the results of a series of optimizations of the form (6) with A_0 varied from 0 dB to -6 dB in 0.1 dB steps and the coefficient dynamic range varied from 5 dB to 30 dB in 5 dB steps. The latter was achieved by varying a_{\min} with a_{\max} fixed at $1/N$. The array geometry and sidelobe region are as in Sec. III. Each design is represented by a circle on the plot, with the series of designs corresponding to a given dynamic-range constraint connected by color-coded lines. At upper left is the limiting case of $A_0 = 0$ dB, which yields uniform weights and a dynamic range of 0 dB. Here all of the dynamic range constraints are inactive, and so all of the colored curves overlap. As A_0 is decreased, rms sidelobes decrease and actual dynamic range increases, until we hit each of the dynamic-range constraint levels. Once the dynamic-range constraint becomes active, further lowering A_0 can further decrease rms sidelobes (the vertical line segments), but only by about 5 dB or so. The dashed diagonal line on the plot shows the rms sidelobe level of the dynamic-range constraint pedestal alone; it shows a very close correspondence with the actual design values when the dynamic range constraint is inactive.

Similar results can be achieved by optimizing peak sidelobes rather than rms sidelobes, which leads to the confirmation that coefficient dynamic range and sidelobe levels are strongly correlated, and we have a fairly limited ability to control them independently.

VI. CONCLUSION

Designing amplitude tapers for transmit arrays requires a somewhat different approach than for receive arrays, owing to the fact that active-array transmitters are generally peak-power limited. In particular, to avoid large ERP losses while suppressing outer sidelobes under a peak-weight constraint it is necessary to allow a few inner sidelobes to remain high. Within this general limitation, there are a number of tradeoffs to be made between ERP, peak and mean-square sidelobes, and dynamic range. Using a general convex constrained optimization such as SOCP allows for a variety of problem formulations. A series of examples was used to demonstrate both the inherent design tradeoffs and several possible problem formulations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was carried out under the Naval Research Laboratory Base Program sponsored by the Office of Naval Research.

Fig. 5: A comparison of the rms sidelobes outside of a 15° radius vs. dynamic range for various dynamic range and peak-gain constraints. The dashed line indicates the level of rms sidelobes that results from the raised pedestal corresponding to the lower dynamic-range bound; its close correspondence to the level that results from unconstrained dynamic range indicates that the sidelobes are largely determined by the pedestal height.

APPENDIX

In the examples it was assumed that the array tapers were real and symmetric. Here, expanding on the brief discussion in [6, Appendix A] it is shown that the resulting responses are indeed optimal over the larger class of complex and asymmetric tapers under certain symmetry conditions.

a) *The optimal a is conjugate symmetric:* Here we will assume that the set of element positions is symmetric through the origin, so that $\{\mathbf{x}_n\} = \{-\mathbf{x}_n\}$. Decompose $a = a_s + a_a$ into conjugate symmetric and antisymmetric components, defined as $a_s(\mathbf{x}) \triangleq \frac{a(\mathbf{x}) + a^*(-\mathbf{x})}{2}$ and $a_a(\mathbf{x}) \triangleq \frac{a(\mathbf{x}) - a^*(-\mathbf{x})}{2}$. The corresponding array-factor decomposition is $A = A_s + A_a$, with A_s and A_a the real and imaginary parts of A , respectively. Since A_0 was previously chosen to be real, we must have $A_a(\mathbf{0}) = 0$, and thus constraint (2b) is unaffected. We have by construction $|A_s(\mathbf{u})| \leq |A_s(\mathbf{u}) + A_a(\mathbf{u})|$ for all \mathbf{u} , and by the triangle inequality we have $\|a_s\|_p = \|\frac{a}{2} + \frac{a'}{2}\|_p \leq \frac{1}{2}\|a\|_p + \frac{1}{2}\|a'\|_p = \|a\|_p = \|a_s + a_a\|_p$, where the penultimate step invokes the invariance of the l^p norm to the paraconjugate operator. Thus any nonzero a_a component can only restrict the corresponding feasible region of a_s in (2) (by increasing the left sides of all of the inequality constraints) and increase the objective, and so at optimality a_a must be zero.

b) *The optimal a is real:* Here we assume that the weighting function W and spectral mask M are symmetric about the origin, so that $W(\mathbf{u}) = W(-\mathbf{u})$ and $M(\mathbf{u}) = M(-\mathbf{u})$. Now decompose $a = a_r + a_i$ into its real and imaginary components, where corresponding array-factor components A_r and A_i are the conjugate symmetric and antisymmetric components of A . Here $A_i(\mathbf{0}) = 0$ by definition, and so again constraint (2b) is

unaffected. By construction we have $|a_r(\mathbf{x})| \leq |a_r(\mathbf{x}) + a_i(\mathbf{x})|$ for all \mathbf{x} , which then implies that $\|a_r\|_p \leq \|a_r + a_i\|_p$. The left sides of constraints (2c) and (2d) are norms (weighted L^2 and L^∞ , respectively) operating on A , and due to the symmetry of W and M they are invariant to paraconjugation. Thus we again invoke the triangle inequality to show that

$$\int W(\mathbf{u})|A_r(\mathbf{u})|^2 d\mathbf{u} \leq \int W(\mathbf{u})|A_r(\mathbf{u}) + A_i(\mathbf{u})|^2 d\mathbf{u}$$

and

$$\sup_{\mathbf{u}}\{M(\mathbf{u})|A_r(\mathbf{u})|\} \leq \sup_{\mathbf{u}}\{M(\mathbf{u})|A_r(\mathbf{u}) + A_i(\mathbf{u})|\}.$$

As before, we see that a nonzero a_i component can only increase the inequality left sides in (2c)–(2f), and thus a_i must be zero at optimality.

When both the array position and the objective/constraints are symmetric, then it follows that the optimal array weights are both real and symmetric. The key to these results is that all of the constraints are either unchanged or tightened by the addition of the imaginary or conjugate-symmetric component. If constraint (2b) was instead of the form

$$\int_{\mathcal{U}_{\text{ml}}} ||A(\mathbf{u}) - D(\mathbf{u})|^2 d\mathbf{u} \leq \delta^2$$

constraining the total square deviation of $|A|$ from some nonzero desired response D over a nonsingleton mainlobe region \mathcal{U}_{ml} , then the optimal a would not be conjugate-symmetric (linear phase) in general [21], [22].

REFERENCES

- [1] C. L. Dolph, "A current distribution for broadside arrays which optimizes the relationship between beam width and side-lobe level," *Proc. I.R.E.*, vol. 34, pp. 335–348, Jun. 1946.
- [2] T. T. Taylor, "Design of line source antennas for narrow beamwidth and low sidelobes," *IRE Trans. Antennas Prop.*, vol. AP-3, p. 16, 1955.
- [3] T. Taylor, "Design of circular apertures for narrow beamwidth and low sidelobes," *IRE Trans. Antennas Prop.*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 17–22, Jan. 1960.
- [4] J. Hoversten, S. Schafer, M. Roberg, M. Norris, D. Maksimovic, and Z. Popovic, "Co-design of PA, supply and signal processing for linear supply-modulated RF transmitters," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Tech.*, vol. 60, no. 6, pp. 2010–2020, Jun. 2012.
- [5] M. Roberg, M. Rodriguez, D. Maksimovic, and Z. Popovic, "Efficient and linear amplification of spectrally confined pulsed AM radar signals," *IEEE Microw. Wireless Compon. Lett.*, vol. 22, no. 6, pp. 279–281, Jun. 2012.
- [6] S. Iglehart, "Design of weighting functions under peak amplitude and effective radiated voltage constraints," *IEEE Trans. Aerosp. Electron. Syst.*, vol. AES-15, no. 2, pp. 267–274, 1979.
- [7] K. Virga and M. Taylor, "Transmit patterns for active linear arrays with peak amplitude and radiated voltage distribution constraints," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 49, no. 5, pp. 732–739, 2001.
- [8] J. A. Rodríguez, F. Ares, and E. Moreno, "Sum pattern side lobe minimization for high-efficiency linear arrays with a uniformly excited central segment," *Journal of Electromagnetic Waves and Applications*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 409–417, 2003.
- [9] S. K. Smith, J. C. Bréguins, K. L. Melde, and F. Ares, "A comparison of optimization techniques for power patterns with low sidelobes generated by linear arrays with efficient excitation distributions," *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 57–60, 2005.
- [10] M. S. Lobo, L. Vandenberghe, S. Boyd, and H. Lebret, "Applications of second-order cone programming," *Linear Algebra and its Applications*, vol. 284, pp. 193–228, Nov. 1998.
- [11] J. O. Coleman and D. P. Scholnik, "Design of nonlinear-phase FIR filters with second-order cone programming," in *Proc. Midwest Symp. on Circuits and Systems*, Las Cruces NM, Aug. 1999.
- [12] D. P. Scholnik and J. O. Coleman, "Optimal array-pattern synthesis for wideband digital transmit arrays," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 660–677, Dec. 2007.
- [13] J. F. Sturm, "Using SeDuMi 1.02, a MATLAB toolbox for optimization over symmetric cones," in *Optimization Methods and Software*, 1999, vol. 11–12, pp. 625–653, special issue on Interior Point Methods.
- [14] K. Toh, M. Todd, and R. Tutuncu, "SDPT3—a matlab software package for semidefinite programming," *Optimization Methods and Software*, vol. 11, pp. 545–581, 1999.
- [15] A. Domahidi, E. Chu, and S. Boyd, "ECOS: an SOCP solver for embedded systems," *European Control Conference*, 2013. [Online]. Available: http://www.stanford.edu/~boyd/papers/pdf/ecos_ecc.pdf
- [16] E. D. Andersen and K. D. Andersen, "The MOSEK interior point optimizer for linear programming: an implementation of the homogeneous algorithm," in *High Performance Optimization*. Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2000, pp. 197–232.
- [17] Gurobi Optimization, Inc., "Gurobi optimizer reference manual," 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://www.gurobi.com>
- [18] J. Coleman, D. Scholnik, and J. Brandriss, "A specification language for the optimal design of exotic FIR filters with second-order cone programs," in *Proc. Asilomar Conf. Signals Syst. Comput.*, vol. 1, 2002, pp. 341–345 vol.1.
- [19] J. Löfberg, "YALMIP : A toolbox for modeling and optimization in MATLAB," in *Proceedings of the CACSD Conference*, Taipei, Taiwan, 2004. [Online]. Available: <http://users.isy.liu.se/johanl/yalmip>
- [20] M. Grant and S. Boyd, "CVX: Matlab software for disciplined convex programming, version 2.1," <http://cvxr.com/cvx>, Mar. 2014.
- [21] S.-P. Wu, S. Boyd, and L. Vandenberghe, "FIR filter design via semidefinite programming and spectral factorization," in *Decision and Control, 1996., Proceedings of the 35th IEEE*, vol. 1, Kobe, Dec. 11–13, 1996, pp. 271–276.
- [22] D. P. Scholnik, "Convex-programming design of linear and nonlinear phase wideband blocking filters," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 59, no. 7, pp. 3133–3142, Jul. 2011.